

Methodology for Increasing the Competitiveness of Participants in the Activities of Small Industry Zones

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Abstract: It is of great importance to study the methodology of effective management of the development of small industrial zones. The article describes the methodology of improving the conceptual foundations of effective management of the development of small industrial zones, increasing competitiveness.

Keywords: small industrial zones, metodologiya, technological modernization, environmental sustainability, social responsibility.

Introduction. The methodology of increasing the competitiveness of the participants of the activity of small industrial zones plays an important role in ensuring socio-economic development. Because every enterprise operating in the industrial zone must be competitive.

Research methodology.

As a research methodology, the risks, studying their group, were used such methods as observation, economic analysis, statistical grouping, comparative and systematic analysis.

The main part.

In order to ensure the high competitiveness of an enterprise that is a participant of small industrial zones, the described sequence of actions should become a model of sustainable management and be repeated many times. In this, only general recommendations can be considered, which are important for increasing the competitiveness of enterprises that are members of the small industrial zone.

First, let's understand the meaning of the word methodology. Methodology is a system of methods and approaches for conducting scientific research, research or work. It consists of theoretical and practical rules, principles and approaches used to conduct work in a particular field.

The methodology usually consists of the following components:

Methods - concrete methods and techniques used to achieve the goal.

Research design is a general approach to how research is structured and conducted.

Theoretical foundations - scientific, theoretical implications and foundations of the methodology.

Principles are basic rules that should be followed in scientific work.

The word methodology itself comes from the Greek words "methodos" (way) and "logos" (doctrine, concept) and means methods of studying and describing research in a certain field of knowledge. .

For example, there are types such as scientific methodology, social research methodology or scientific-technical methodology.

The methodology of increasing the competitiveness of the participants of the activity of small industrial zones can play an important role in ensuring socio-economic development. Special strategies and methods have been developed for this, which may include:

1. Increase production efficiency

Technological modernization: teaching KSZ participants to use modern, energy-efficient and environmentally friendly techniques.

Automation and Digitization: Automation of production processes, improvement of production efficiency through the use of digital technologies and intelligent systems.

Production Optimization: Production optimization to run industrial processes at lower cost.

2. Product quality improvement

Quality control systems: quality assurance according to international standards such as ISO, GOST.

Innovative features of the product: Use of innovative technologies to produce new and competitive products.

Product branding and marketing: Strengthening the product's position in the market through effective branding and advertising.

3. Creating favorable economic conditions

Financial and credit support: financial support through loans, grants and preferential loans for KSZ participants.

Subsidies and incentives: Support of small and medium-sized businesses through state subsidies, incentives and other financial assistance.

Staff training and retraining: Training of participants, training of specialists with knowledge and skills in newly added fields.

4. Education and establishment of reliable partnerships

Research and Development (R&D): Investment in research and development to upgrade production and introduce new technologies.

Production collaborations: joint work among KSZ participants, increasing competitiveness through the use of common resources.

Market Research: Every manufacturer needs to study the market and adapt to it.

5. Environmental and social responsibility

Environmental sustainability: Working in ecological directions, complying with environmental standards and introducing new, clean technologies.

Social responsibility: Involvement in social projects, ensuring the protection of workers and improving the lifestyle of the general population.

6. Localization of production

Use of raw materials: production and efficient use of local raw materials in KSZ.

Local production chains: Collaborating with local producers in product creation.

These methodologies are necessary steps for sustainable development of small industrial zones, efficient organization of production and increasing competitiveness.

Participants of activities of small industrial zones (KSZ) can be:

Small and medium-sized business entities are the main producers working in KSZ. These entities contribute to economic development by employing skilled workers and producing new products.

Firms and enterprises — Organizations engaged in production and service in various industries. By moving to KSZ, they aim to increase their production capacity and strengthen their competitiveness.

Large industrial enterprises — These enterprises can cooperate with KSZ, introduce new production lines or send some parts of details to production by outsourcing.

Providers of technical and scientific services are enterprises or specialists who provide scientific and technical support necessary for increasing the efficiency of KSZs. These types of services include, for example, the improvement of technologies and production processes.

Credit and financial organizations — banks or other financial organizations engaged in providing financial support and granting loans to entities operating in KSZs.

Educational and personnel training institutions — educational institutions engaged in the training of qualified personnel for KSZ, retraining of workers and improvement of their qualifications.

State bodies - state bodies participate by regulating the activities of KSZ, monitoring them and providing them with legislation. These bodies may include local authorities.

Also, among the entities operating in KSZ, there may be individuals and companies cooperating in terms of logistics, financial support, and supply of raw materials.

Conclusions and suggestions:

Based on the above, the following conclusions can be drawn to increase and manage the competitiveness of the enterprise:

- 1) collecting and processing information about the company's activities and competitors in the market;
- 2) analysis and grouping of the collected primary data, assessment of the level of competitiveness of the enterprise and setting specific goals for maintaining or improving this level;
- 3) development of an enterprise strategy aimed at purposefully increasing the level of competitiveness;
- 4) increase the consistency of the strategy in the development process and in the planning of management decisions;
- 5) implementation of competitive strategy by organizing events;
- 6) during the analysis of the achieved results, to study the competitiveness of the enterprise, to observe the main stages of the implementation of the strategy, as well as to adjust the strategies again if necessary.

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